

International Scientific Conference "Genealogy of Conspirituality in Europe"

Dear colleagues,
You are kindly invited to participate in the international conference "Genealogy of Conspirituality in Europe," held **on May 15–16, 2025**.

The conference is organised by the "Genealogy of Conspirituality in 20th Century Latvia" project at the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the Faculty of Humanities of the University of Latvia.

The conference aims to explore the intricate relationship between conspiracy theories and spirituality, a phenomenon gaining momentum within Europe's cultural and academic discourse. The focus is on understanding the genealogy of conspirituality, mapping its historical roots, and dissecting its socio-political implications in contemporary society.

Conference Key Themes

Historical Roots and Evolution: Examination of the origins of conspirituality in Western esoteric traditions, tracing its evolution into the modern-day amalgamation of conspiracy theories and New Age spirituality.

Cultural and Political Dimensions: Exploration of how conspirituality acts as both a spiritual practice and a political instrument across various European contexts, highlighting local variations in narratives, practices, and rituals.

Psychological and Social Functions: This section analyses conspirituality as a mechanism for individual and societal adaptation in times of crisis, including its role in providing a sense of control, community, and identity.

Comparative Analyses: Cross-disciplinary perspectives on conspirituality, encouraging comparative studies in religious practices, conspiracy theory subcultures, and societal impacts.

Conference Structure

Keynote Speeches: Leading scholars in religious studies, history, psychology, and cultural studies will be invited to give keynote speeches.

Presentations: Opportunities for researchers to present their findings, facilitating further discussions and networking among participants.

Panel Discussions: Focused on the specific research questions outlined in the conference goals, these sessions will facilitate in-depth debates among experts, scholars, and attendees.

Conference venue: remotely on the ZOOM platform.

The working language of the conference will be **English**.

We intend to publish the conference papers (after editing and peer review) in a special publication of our journal *Reliģiski-filozofiski raksti* (Religious-Philosophical Articles), indexed by SCOPUS.

Organising Committee:

Dr Solveiga Krūmiņa-Koņkova
Dr. Māra Kiope
Dr. Inese Runce

Deadline:

The deadline for proposals is **November 29, 2024**.

If you want to participate in the conference, please fill in the form, which you will find here: <https://forms.gle/PtV8smtwpdXkTC826>

If you have any questions, please email: solveiga.krumina-konkova@lu.lv

Response with acceptance of papers: **December 27, 2024**.

Please note that only selected participants will receive an e-mail confirming their abstracts.

We look forward to receiving your application!

Sincerely,

The Organising Committee